

Gender STI

D5.2 – Communication and Dissemination Mid-term Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The following report will present the results of the Gender STI project's Communication and Dissemination Plan—which can be examined in-depth in D5.1: Communication and Dissemination Plan—during the first 18 months of the action.

Overall, the project has been received with enthusiasm by the European and international science, technology, and innovation (STI) community, many of whom acknowledge the importance of promoting gender equality in international STI cooperation. It remains to be seen to what level this belief in gender equality extends to action in bilateral and multilateral STI agreements. However, initial research shows that the gender perspective is not frequently mentioned.

The project's communication and dissemination activities have met all of the expected KPIs for the first reporting period, exceeding them in many cases. In addition, engagement with the project's activities has also been high, producing collaborations with the European Commission itself and Gender STI's sister projects in gender equality.

These results have caused us to be highly optimistic about what the project will be able to accomplish during its second and third years. We have no doubt that Gender STI will make a profound impact in the area of gender equality in international cooperation.

1 INTRODUCTION

This report will discuss the implementation and mid-term results of the Gender STI Communication and Dissemination Plan. It will describe the key actions and activities carried out in communication as well as dissemination.

As a reference, the objectives for communication and dissemination are laid out below:

- Introduce the project to GENDER STI's target audiences;
- Create a deeper understanding of the GENDER STI project and its objectives;
- Promote GENDER STI and raise awareness about it;
- Transfer GENDER STI knowledge and outcomes to stakeholder groups that can use the information;
- Create synergies with ERA-related groups;
- Create synergies with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, in particular with SwafS projects; and
- Engage with key stakeholder groups to obtain feedback on project results.

Section 1 of the report will present the project's communication activities, including email campaigns, social media campaigns, and project events, among others. Considering that Gender STI is a research and innovation project and that results are not available immediately, we focused on communication activities to raise the project's profile among stakeholder communities and foment gender equality in STI on an international level.

Section 2 will discuss Gender STI's dissemination activities, which are directly related to the project's results. Gender STI has only recently started publishing official results, such as the insights gained from our "Survey Report on Gender Equality Implementation in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements." We have transferred the knowledge gained from this research to our target audiences and expect to disseminate even more results in the following reporting period.

Section 3 will go through the project's online metrics and overall key performance indicators. We will report on the traffic to the Gender STI website since the beginning of the project, the amount of time people spent on the site, the geographic location of the visitors, and the most popular pages and posts, among other metrics. In addition, we will present a status update on the communication and dissemination KPIs.

Section 4 will outline the next steps in the project's communication and dissemination plan for the second reporting period.

Section 5 will present the conclusion.

2 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In accordance with the project's Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.1), we focused on efforts on communication activities during the first reporting period. This was done because Gender STI, as a research and innovation project, would not have many results to disseminate immediately. By dedicating ourselves to communication activities, we ensured that the project became known to target audiences, formed links to sister projects, became known as a relevant voice in the STI field, and fomented a message of gender equality in STI.

Our communication activities consisted of the following: social media and web campaigns, email campaigns, attending third party events, hosting Gender STI events, and participating in joint campaigns with our sister projects.

Overall, these communication activities established a solid base for Gender STI to later use to transfer knowledge from its investigations. This base proved to be extremely useful when we disseminated the project's first results, which consisted of the "Survey Report on Gender Equality Implementation in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements" and the "Report on Gender STI Co-Design Labs I" in the last months of the first reporting period.

2.1 Campaigns

2.1.1 *#WomenInScience Campaign — International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2021*

Figure 1: Graphic for IDWGS 2021 Campaign

Gender STI launched its first social media and web campaign from Feb. 8 – 12, 2021 during the week of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science (IDWGS). The campaign shared the stories of experts involved in the project, as well as select sister projects, who explained why they decided to work in STI and described what

needs to be done to encourage more women and girls to pursue scientific careers (annex 1).

The campaign was launched on Gender STI's social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter) and on the project's website. In addition, our team communicated the campaign to the European Commission's Research Executive Agency, which then magnified the campaign on its social channels.

Figure 2: Examples of Social Media Posts for IDWGS 2021

A summary of the campaign's results is provided below.

- **Total Organic Impressions Across All Channels:** 62,384 impressions (views) on LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook + Gender STI Website
- **Total Organic Engagements:** 1,739
- **LinkedIn Engagement Rate:** 7.10%**
- **Twitter Engagement Rate:** 2.60%*
- **Facebook Engagement Rate:** 2.20%*

(Engagements: This refers to the number of times people have interacted with the publication, and includes likes, shares, retweets and clicks, among others.

(Organic: This refers to views and interactions that have been generated without running paid campaigns. The entire campaign was organic.

*** Far above industry average for organic campaign. * Above industry average for organic campaign).*

Figure 3: Final IDWGS 2021 Blog Post

In total, we featured 22 amazing researchers and experts, both men and women, from across the world. Although all of them expressed different views on the state of gender equality in STI, they agreed on one key point: Women make science better (annex 2).

2.1.2 #WomenInLeadership Campaign — International Women's Day 2021

Figure 4: Graphic for IWD 2021 Campaign

Following a successful IDWGS campaign, we quickly got to work on our campaign for International Women's Day on March 8. Considering that the United Nations' 2021 theme for the worldwide celebration centered on "leadership," we decided to focus on women leaders in STI. Our team asked our international partners to nominate

women in their institutions, countries, or fields who were exemplary leaders and got an overwhelmingly positive response (annex 3).

The campaign featured interviews with women leaders, focusing on the challenges they faced in their leadership journey, their goals as a leader, and the advice they would give young girls who want to be leaders in their fields one day. The initiative was launched on Gender STI's social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter) and on the project's website.

Figure 5: Examples of Social Media Posts for IWD 2021

Our team informed the European Research Agency of the planned activities as well as the consortium's partner institutions and the nominees' institutions. All entities contacted promoted the project and the #WomenInLeadership campaign, which resulted in a far-reaching and impactful action.

Campaign Social Media Mentions

Our #WomenInLeadership campaign was shared by 32 partner and third-party entities, including universities, research groups, companies and state governments. The campaign received support from:

- Biocon
- Fiocruz
- Know-Center
- TU Graz
- CSIR
- CIHR
- São Paulo Secretary for Economic Development, Science and Technology Patricia Ellen
- Georgia Tech

- University of Manitoba
- University of Montreal
- Centre de recherche du Centre hospitalier de l'Université de Montréal
- IDRC
- OCAD University
- University of Alberta
- WISDOM
- University of South Africa
- We Count
- CNRS
- Inmark
- Society for Canadian Women in Science & Technology
- Instituto de Estudos Brasil Europa
- Canadian VIGOUR Centre
- University of Alberta Faculty of Medicine & Dentistry
- UNISA Research
- Pocket Code
- Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada
- Journal of the International Network for Engineering Studies
- Girls in ICT Spain
- Le Centre intersectoriel d'analyse des perturbateurs endocriniens
- Agência FAPESP
- POLI USP
- Centro México Digital
- REUNA

Partner institutions and third-party entities also published more than 10 news articles about the campaign and shared them on their websites. More examples can be found in annex 4.

Figure 6: Example of Third-Party Campaign Mentions

A breakdown of the campaign's results is provided below:

- **Total Organic Views Across All Channels:** 306,070 views on LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook + Gender STI Website
- **Total Organic Engagements:** 6,557
- **LinkedIn Engagement Rate:** 2.92%*
- **Twitter Engagement Rate:** 1.52%*
- **Facebook Engagement Rate:** 2.72%*

(Engagements: This refers to the number of times people have interacted with the publication, and includes likes, shares, retweets and clicks, among others.

Organic: This refers to views and interactions that have been generated without running paid campaigns.

** In line with or above industry average for organic campaign).*

Figure 7: Final Blog Post for IWD 2021

In total, we featured 22 extraordinary women from 11 countries across the globe, from professors and researchers to business executives and political leaders.

2.1.3 #DreamItBelt Joint Social Media Campaign With Sister Projects — International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2022

Figure 8: Graphic for IDWGS Joint Campaign 2022

International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2022

On the International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2022, the EU Sister projects: CALIPER, GEARING ROLES, Gender-SMART, SUPERA, LeTSGEPs, RESET, SPEAR, CASPER, ACT, GenPORT, MINDtheGEPs, ATHENA, GRANteD, EQUAL4EUROPE, Gender STI are joining forces and sharing positive stories to encourage other women and especially young girls, to become engaged with Research & Innovation.

#DreamItBeIt

If you are a women researcher join us using our # and tell us

- What is your professional background?
- What did inspire you to pursue this career?
- Who was your role model?

#EUSisterProjects

All the projects are funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134, 824546, 787829, 873072, 101006560, 824544, 872113, 788204, 321485, 101006543, 101006416, 824574, 824536, 872499, 872427

For the International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2022, Gender STI joined forces with its fellow EU Sister Projects in gender equality on the #DreamItBeIt campaign, which took place on Feb. 11. The campaign aimed to highlight key women in STI and share what inspired them to pursue their career as well as who they looked to as a role model. Gender STI asked its consortium partners to nominate women in STI inside and outside of their organizations for this campaign.

The campaign was carried out on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook), with each Sister Project nominating a series of women scientists and sharing their stories the week on Feb. 11.

In total, 15 Sister Projects participated in the #DreamItBeIt campaign. The initiative was reported to the Commission and promoted by Horizon Europe social channels.

Figure 9: Examples of Social Media for IDWGS 2022

As this was a joint campaign, a breakdown of the results is not available.

2.1.4 Twitter Chain Joint Social Media Campaign With #EUSisterProjects – International Women’s Day 2022

Figure 10: Graphic for IWD 2022 Campaign

EU Sister Projects on gender equality, including Gender STI, came together again for International Women’s Day 2022 on March 8. This time, Gender STI and its Sister Projects decided to carry out a novel campaign that consisted of a Twitter chain under the hashtag #EUSisterProjects.

The campaign aimed to showcase the work being done by each Sister Project and build upon it. Put simply: a project started the chain with a tweet on its purpose and results and another project responded to it with the same information. The idea was to create digital “links” between all Sister Projects, therefore showcasing the dedication to gender equality in Europe.

Figure 11: Example of Tweet Chain for IWD 2022

Figure 12: Example of Social Media for IWD 2022

In total, 19 Sister Projects participated in the campaign. The initiative was supported by the Commission's European Research Executive Agency.

2.2 Events

GENDER STI has organized and attended events related to gender equality as a way to promote the project and increase engagement with key stakeholders in the field of STI, across Europe and third countries.

2.2.1 Project events

First Co-Design Labs. September-October 2021

The first Co-Design Lab addressed the biggest issues facing women in three key focus areas: scientific careers, decision-making, and the gender perspective in research and innovation content. The Labs have created a meaningful environment to co-create and prototype solutions related to the three forefront challenges to promote gender equality in R&I.

Due to Covid19 restrictions the first Co-Design Lab was performed through online sessions. Two series of Labs were implemented to facilitate the participation across four continents: Europe-America (WEST Lab) and Europe-South Africa-Asia (EAST Lab). Overall, the Co-Design Labs were attended by 70 participants (42 for the WEST and 28 for the EAST) from 19 countries. As a result, 12 prototypes were initially

designed in the first Labs, based on design thinking principles. These prototypes were merged in 7 prototypes so as to create more robust solutions for the three challenges.

- 2 Prototypes on gender equality in scientific careers that set up actions to support a cultural change at universities by creating a welcoming atmosphere and develop an international agreement to increase the representation of women in STI careers.
- 2 Prototypes on gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions that focus on the promotion of female networks that empower women in STI and development of a guideline to support gender mainstreaming in the process of setting up agreements for decision-making positions.
- 3 Prototypes on the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content that aim to develop a methodology based on inclusive design for R&I funding agencies, a training programme on how to embed inclusive thinking and create a tool for monitoring and supporting gender integration into R&I content.

After the Co-Design Labs, all participants were invited to join the project's Community of Practice (CoP), which aims to promote gender equality in STI across European and third countries.

Workshop on "Integrating the Gender Perspective in STI" at IEEE BHI – BSN. 27 July 2021.

The workshop was organized by Maria Fernanda Cabrera (UPM) and Yolanda Ursa (INMARK), with the participation of partners from Mexico (ITESM), India (EIRC) and South Africa (CSIR). The workshop featured top women scientists, policy experts, and higher education professionals from multiple continents and addressed challenges associated with integrating the gender perspective in STI as well as work towards gender equality.

The aim of the workshop was to leverage participants' knowledge, diversity, background in policy dialogues and gender expertise to discuss a strategy to promote gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision making and the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content. The workshop started with brief presentations by the panel members about how gender perspectives are tackled in the different STI activities they are involved in, highlighting the issues and challenges affecting the careers of women in STI. Following the presentations, there was an interactive discussion aiming to collect different initiatives, proposals and ideas to address gender equality, where panellists answered questions from audience members. Attendees collectively discussed issues and strategies within IEEE-EMBS BHI and BSN for promoting and addressing gender equality in science, technology and innovation.

2.2.2 Third party events

Events attended by GENDER STI partners:

- Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Summit 2021. Opal Group. New York, USA (Virtual). 4 February 2021.
- ACT Project: 2nd ACT International Synergy Conference. Jagiellonian University. Krakow, Poland (Virtual) 11-12 February 2021.
- Women in science, overcoming stereotypes and inequalities. Fundación la Caixa. Madrid, Spain (Virtual). 11 February 2021.

- SUPERA Project: How covid-19 impacted on gender equality in research and academia. Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Madrid, Spain (Virtual). 9 March 2021.
- TARGET-GEECCO Conference. TU Wien. Wien, Austria (Virtual). 11 March 2021.
- S4D4C Final Networking Meeting: Addressing Global Challenges Together: The Role of Science Diplomacy. Centre for Social Innovation. Wien, Austria (Virtual) 15-19 March 2021.
- CALIPER project: Gender summit: Gender Equality, Diversity, Inclusion post-Corona: Quo vadis?. Thessaloniki, Greece (Virtual). 14-16 April 2021.
- EU-Canada Cooperation Workshop in AI: Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in Artificial Intelligence. Global Affairs Canada. Quebec, Canada (Virtual). 26-28 April 2021.
- Women at the Vanguard of the New Economies. NU Women. Santiago de Chile, Chile (Virtual). 30 April 2021.
- United Nations Commission on Science and Technology for Development: 24th Session. Geneva, Switzerland (Virtual) 17-21 May 2021.
- The Generation Equality Forum: a historic global feminist event. UN Women. Paris, France. (Virtual). 30 June-2 July 2021.
- XIII Iberoamerican Congress on Science, Technology and Gender. Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture. Quito, Ecuador (Virtual). 14-16 July 2021.
- TICAL2021 conference and 5th Latin American e-Science Meeting. Red CLARA (Virtual). 30 August– 2 September 2021.
- EBN Congress 2021. European Business and Innovation Centre Network. Brussels, Belgium (Virtual). 14-15 September 2021.
- 38th IASP World Conference on Science Parks and Areas of Innovation. IASP. Málaga, Spain (Virtual). 28-30 September 2021
- Science and Technology in Society forum: 18th Annual Meeting. STS forum. Kyoto, Japan. (Virtual). 2-5 October 2021.
- IEEE Healthcare Summit: Integrating BHI and AI to Combat Pandemics. IEEE Advanced Technology for Humanity. New York, USA (Virtual). 4-7 October 2021.
- Scientific Diplomacy and Gender: Cooperation in Science and Sustainable Development with a Gender Perspective. Organization for Women in Science for the Developing World- Uruguay. Montevideo, Uruguay (Virtual). 19 October 2021.
- 20th Mexican International Conference on Artificial Intelligence. Mexican Society for Artificial Intelligence. Mexico City, Mexico (Virtual). 25-30 October 2021.
- Brain and Women II. Buenos Aires, Argentina (Virtual). 26 November 2021.
- ACTIVAS Program: Women Internationalizing and Curricularizing the Gender Perspective. Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata. Buenos Aires, Argentina. 9 December 2021.
- Mission for the place of women. CNRS. 20 ans d'engagement pour l'égalité professionnelle au CNRS. Acteurs et actions: de l'échelle du laboratoire aux partenariats internationaux. Paris, France (Virtual). 11 January 2022.

- French Presidency of the council of the European Union - France 22: Gender Equality in Higher Education, Research and Innovation: from institutional policies to international cooperation. Paris, France (Virtual). 10 February 2022.
- Workshop Women in Science. Sao Paulo University. Sao Paulo, Brazil (Virtual). 8 March 2022.
- EU-LAC Women as Key Actors in Climate Action and Disaster Prevention - Launching of the EU-LAC Women's International Network. EU-LAC Foundation. Hamburg, Germany (Virtual). 23 March 2022.
- Launching of the Innovation in Higher Education (InES) Gender Project. Universidad de Chile. Santiago de Chile, Chile (Virtual). 23 March 2022.
- SUPERA final conference: Beyond ticking the box. Sustainable, innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans. Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Madrid, Spain. 25 March 2022.

3 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

As mentioned previously, we've focused largely on communication activities during this reporting period because our results are not to be published until later on. However, we did publish our first small batch of results in the second half of 2022, which consisted of the "Survey Report" and the "Report on Gender STI Co-Design Labs".

We disseminated these results through several channels, presenting them directly at events, publishing them on a dedicated section of our website, and transferring them to stakeholders in STI via email campaigns and social media.

Events

Gender STI has already begun disseminating results at third-party and project organized events, such as the Co-Design Labs. Survey results were shared at the Co-Design Labs and participants were encouraged to provide their feedback.

CEREBRO Y MUJER II
MITOS, REALIDADES, DISTINTAS PERSPECTIVAS

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Equidad de género y producción de conocimiento: impactos y desafíos en el mundo post-covid19

Derribando mitos sobre la "objetividad" del conocimiento: la importancia de **avanzar hacia una agenda** de ciencia y tecnología feminista

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Lo personal es político y lo académico también: ¿cuándo y cómo el género deviene o no agenda de investigación?

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Scientific papers

The consortium partners have submitted several abstracts and papers related to the project results to conferences and scientific journals:

- Yolanda Ursa, Mariel Bleger, Lara Primosich, Ana Franchi, Silvia Kochen, Luciana Ayciriex (2021), **Equidad de género en la Cooperación Internacional en Ciencia Tecnología e innovación**. XIII Congreso Iberoamericano de Ciencia, Tecnología y Género, Quito-Ecuador, 14 July 2021.

- Maria F Cabrera, Yolanda Ursa (2021), **Integrating Gender perspective in Science, Technology and Innovation**. IEEE-EMBS BHI 2021 - IEEE-EMBS International Conference on Biomedical and Health Informatics (BHI), Conference-poster, 27 July 2021.
- Sarina Gursch, Katja Urak, Michael Herold, Stefan Kutschera, Maria Fernanda Cabrera, Yolanda Ursa, Wolfgang Slany, Vesna Krnjic (2022), **Inequalities for Women in Science, Technology and Innovation**. International Conference on Gender Research – ICGR 2022, Conference proceedings, University of Aveiro, Portugal, 28 - 29 April 2022.
- Riina Bhatia, Maria Merisalo, Nina Rilla and Tuisku Salonen (2022), **Challenging Science and Innovation Policy. From persisting gender inequality to inclusion in research and innovation content: challenging the gender equality norm in the STI fields**. Extended abstract to Eu-SPRI 2022 conference, Utrecht, 1-3 June 2022.
- Maria F. Cabrera, Yolanda Ursa (2022), **Towards Gender Equality in Science, Technology and Innovation**. IUPESM World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering, Singapore, 12-17 June 2022.

Publications

The project has set up a section of its website exclusively for results titled "Publications." Initial reports are provided free of charge to anyone interested. Additionally, this page is routinely promoted on Gender STI's social media channels to foment interest in project results.

The reports on this page are preliminary. Once they are accepted and approved by the Commission, we will update the page with the final versions.

Figure 13: "Publications" Page on Gender STI Website

Email campaigns

Importantly, Gender STI has directly transferred results to identified stakeholders in STI who are interested in gender equality. We have created a series of targeted email campaigns with our project results.

Campaigns have been sent to the users who subscribe to our newsletter on the website, the members of our Community of Practice, Advisory Board, ERA groups, EU Sister Projects, EU funding agencies, and third country funding and other state agencies.

Examples of additional email campaigns can be found in annex 5.

4 ONLINE METRICS AND KPIS

A big part of Gender STI’s communication and dissemination plan is its website. The website is the project’s digital hub that explains its purpose, shares its activities, and hosts its project results, among many other things.

We’re thrilled to report that Gender STI’s website has surpassed expectations of traffic and engagement for the first reporting period. Nonetheless, there are still areas we can improve on, but this is a great start. A breakdown of the data from Google Analytics is provided in the following section.

Figure 14: Gender STI Website Traffic Since Launch

Website traffic since its launch in January 2021 to March 2022 reached 8,300. We acknowledge that the average amount of engagement time could be increased. Yet, we also want to point out that the website was built with a focus on an explanatory landing page. In other words, a person can read the landing page and find out the essential elements of the project in a quick and simple way.

Figure 15: Traffic Breakdown by Source

The traffic breakdown by source is also positive. It shows that the majority of the website’s visitors reach it via a direct pathway, i.e., they type in the website or go directly to the website. Organic (unpaid) search is also a good indicator because it demonstrates that the project has successfully positioned the website according to SEO best practices. Organic (unpaid) social is an important factor as well, a reflection of the high engagement the project receives on social media.

Figure 16: Average Visitor Time Spent on Site

The average engagement time is the average amount of time a visitor spends on the website. As mentioned above, while this number (32 seconds) isn’t entirely unexpected because of the website’s very design, we want to improve and want people to spend more time on the Gender STI website and its various sections.

Figure 17: Most Popular Webpages

Page title and screen class	Views	Users
Totals	15,298 100% of total	8,308 100% of total
1 A research project on Gender Equality - Gender STI	6,506	5,318
2 What is Gender STI? - Gender STI	948	625
3 About Us - Gender STI	661	447
4 News & Events - Gender STI	633	275
5 Publications - Gender STI	556	310
6 22 Lessons From Women Leaders for International Women's Day 2021	546	431
7 Aleksandra Krstikj IWD 2021: "All Women Leaders Today Are Icebreakers"	329	246
8 European Observatory on Gender in STI - Gender STI	287	199
9 Gender STI Launches #WomenInLeadership Campaign for IWD 2021	278	192
10 Gender STI Launches Survey on International Cooperation in STI	257	170

The most popular webpages visited on the Gender STI reinforce our hypothesis about the landing page. It's the most visited page, which can indicate that visitors are getting all of the information they seek from that page.

Nonetheless, the fact that there is a mix of pages in the most popular webpage section is a good indication. It allows us to infer that visitors are interested in many aspects of our project and website. In addition, the inclusion of blogs in this site, such as the post on "22 Lessons From Women Leaders for International Women's Day 2021," is also an indication that our target audiences are reading our content.

Figure 18: Traffic Breakdown by Country

Country ▾	+	↓ Users	New users
Totals		8,308 100% of total	8,265 100% of total
1 United States		3,828	3,794
2 Canada		444	442
3 Spain		421	419
4 New Zealand		417	417
5 Brazil		349	347
6 India		332	331
7 Mexico		190	190
8 Austria		181	181
9 Finland		145	145
10 Italy		140	139

The geographic profiles of the website's visitors are a welcome result. Gender STI is an international project with participation from European and third countries, including countries in North America, South America, Asia, and Africa. High numbers of European, North, and South American visitors demonstrate that we are reaching our target audiences. However, we would like to see more visitors from Africa and Asia and will work on targeting those audiences in the next reporting period.

4.1 Communication Quantitative and Qualitative Indicators

In this section, we will detail the quantitative and qualitative indicators for communication and dissemination established in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.1).

Table 1: Update on Communication Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Status	Detail
Availability of GENDER STI website	Website online 24/7	Met	Website is online 24/7 since M2.
Website visits	3,000 visits	Met	8,265 visits
Social media followers	Twitter: 300 Facebook: 100 LinkedIn: 50	Met	Twitter: 310 Facebook: 100 LinkedIn: 403
Project news articles on website	30 articles.	Met	62 articles.
Third-Party events attended by project partners	At least 20 events.	Met	More than 20.
Number of presentations about the project at third-party events	At least 10 presentations.	Met	More than 10.
Promotional actions carried out by partners on their online channels	At least 10 actions.	Met	More than 10.
Newsletters	At least one each quarter.	In progress	Two sent in 2021; four planned for 2022.
Participate in joint meetings of bi-regional dialogues between EU and third countries	At least one meeting for each region partner of the project (Latin America, Asia, Africa and North America).	In progress	TBA
Attendees to project Co-Design Labs	At least 50.	Met	70 participants

Table 2: Update on Communication Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Status	Detail
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions on online channels.	Met	Gender STI has established itself as a leading initiative in the gender equality space and is frequently mentioned by Sister Projects, partner institutions, and the Commission.
Proactive online community	Community that engages with the project's content.	Met	Gender STI has a high level of engagement with its publications and actions and has met or surpassed social media KPIs.
Contributions to other actions	Requests for contribution from the project can be seen as an example of its influence among stakeholders.	Met	Gender STI has acted as a leader in inviting Sister Projects to participate in its initiatives. Similarly, it has also been invited to participate in and promote the initiatives of Sister Projects.

4.2 Dissemination Quantitative Indicators

Next, we will present a status update on the dissemination quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Table 3: Update on Dissemination Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Status	Detail
Number of attendees to Project Co-Design Labs	At least 50	Met	70 participants
Email campaigns with project results	At least two	Met	At least four
Number of citations of project results in online channels	10	Met	More than 10
Number of visits to project publications page	200	Met	556
Number of visits to Observatory page	200	Met	287
Publish papers on GENDER STI results in scientific journals	-	Met	5 abstracts or papers
Number of policy briefs on GENDER STI research findings and recommendations	One in M18 and one in M36	Met	Policy brief in M18
Number of attendees to project final event	-	Pending	N/A

Table 4: Update on Dissemination Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	Reporting Period 1	Status	Detail
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions of project results on online channels.	Met	Gender STI has been frequently mentioned by EU Sister Projects and other gender equality initiatives. It has also been promoted by state-level funding agencies, including Brazil's FAPESP and Canada's CIHR.
Proactive online community	Scientific community that engages with project's results and adds to the conversation.	Met	High-level women scientists have engaged with and promoted the project's gender equality message and promoted its first results.
Contributions to other actions	Requests for contribution, specifically project results, from the project can be seen as an example of its influence among stakeholders.	In progress	Gender STI has just published its first batch of results. We anticipate that these requests for contribution will increase in the second reporting period.

5 NEXT STEPS IN COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

Throughout the next reporting period, we will continue to follow our D.1 "Communication and Dissemination Plan," which has so far met or surpassed our expectations for impact. Nonetheless, the team will monitor results closely and will make modifications in the plan if needed.

Focus on meeting reporting period 2 KPIs

We have successfully met nearly all of our quantitative and qualitative KPIs in the first reporting period, at times greatly exceeding expectations. The project undoubtedly has created an impact over the past year and possesses momentum. Therefore, our focus is now on meeting our KPIs for reporting period 2, which can be found in D5.1

Promotion of project and its activities

Our team will continue to use communication to promote the project and its activities by launching web and social media campaigns and engaging with Sister Projects. We believe that communication is essential to lay the groundwork for successful dissemination of project results. Our communication activities allow us to connect and maintain contact with our target audiences. These are the same groups to which we seek to disseminate our project results.

In addition, our communication activities allow us to foment gender equality in STI on an international level, which is one of our project's goals.

Beginning of intense dissemination campaign of project results

Gender STI is expecting to produce the bulk of our project results in the second reporting period. Once results are published, we will begin an intense dissemination campaign online, on social media, and in-person (if possible) to transfer knowledge to target audiences and Sister Projects.

Hosting of Co-Design Labs

We will host our two final Co-Design Lab workshops online and in-person (if possible). Building on the knowledge and experience gained from Co-Design Lab I, we will craft workshops to focus on key issues surrounding gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements. Our goal will be to produce insights as well as key courses for action and policy recommendations.

Hosting of Final Event

In the upcoming reporting period, we will host a final project event online or in-person (if possible). The event will present our research findings, publications, Co-Design Lab results, and recommendations to increase gender equality in international cooperation with Europe and third countries.

Considering the positive results provided by Gender STI's Communication and Dissemination Plan, we believe it is not necessary to provide a risk assessment plan at this time. Risks of falling behind on our planned goals is small.

6 CONCLUSION

Overall, Gender STI is in a solid position when it comes to communication and dissemination. It has succeeded in establishing itself as a must-watch EU-funded project in STI and gender equality and had formed meaningful partnerships with other EU Sister Projects related to its research.

Gender STI is an active initiative, continuously launching and participating in communication activities to promote the project. In terms of dissemination, it is off to a good start and has already transferred the knowledge gained from the "Survey Report on Gender Equality Implementation in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements" and the "Report on Co-Design Labs I." Consortium members are also highly engaged and participate in third-party events to present the project. They also write scientific documents and papers about the project to share its research with the R&I community.

The next reporting period will be a busy one for the project because it will produce the majority of its results at this time. However, it is clear that Gender STI has successfully established a groundwork to support itself and ensure its success in this next phase, thereby demonstrating its high commitment to gender equality in STI.

ANNEX 1 – BLOG FOR IDWGS 2021 I

Gender STI Launches #WomenInScience Campaign for the International Day of Women and Girls in Science

NEWS

08.02.2021

The Gender STI project is thrilled to participate in the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, the annual effort to promote full and equal access to and participation in science for women and girls carried out by the United Nation’s Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women (UN Women).

History of February 11th

Every year since 2016, UNESCO and UN Women observe the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, which takes place on Feb. 11. The event aims to use education and public awareness-raising activities to promote the full and equal participation of women and girls in education, training, employment and decision-making processes in science. Participants also advocate for the elimination of all discrimination against women in science and the breaking of legal, economic, social and cultural barriers preventing them from getting involved in science.

In a statement, Phumzile Mlambo-Ngcuka, Under-Secretary-General of the United Nations and Executive Director of UN Women, highlighted that we still have a long way to go to tackle the challenges for women and girls in science.

“Less than 30% of the world’s researchers are women, with studies showing that women in STEM are published less, paid less for their research and do not advance as far as men in their careers,” Mlambo-Ngcuka said. “We need to break gender stereotypes that link science to masculinity and expose young generations to positive role models.”

From Gender STI's perspective, this knowledge is troubling, and only reinforces our commitment to analyze gender equality in dialogues between Europe and third countries and propose solutions to challenges faced with regards to gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision making and the integration of the gender dimension in R&I content.

Gender STI #WomenInScience Campaign

As part of our contribution to the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, we'll be sharing the stories of researchers and experts involved in the Gender STI project, many of which are incredible women, all week. Our partners will explain why they decided to work in science, technology and innovation, share their reactions to current statistics about women researchers and describe what they think needs to be done to encourage more girls and women to pursue scientific careers.

In addition, we'll also be featuring input from researchers and experts involved in our sister projects, which also study and promote gender equality. We are so excited to be a part of a passionate community of researchers and experts striving to ensure women have the place they deserve in science.

Follow our campaign using the hashtags #WomenInScience, which is the official hashtag used by UNESCO and UN Women, and #GenderSTI. Although the International Day of Women and Girls in Science is only this week, it should be celebrated every day. Women and girls are doing amazing things in science all the time, and they need our support. When we fully support our women and girls, there are no limits to what our society will be able to accomplish.

ANNEX 2 – BLOG FOR IDWGS 2021 II

Women Make Science Better: Gender STI Interviews Researchers and Experts on Equality in Science

NEWS

12.02.2021

In honor of the [International Day of Women and Girls in Science](#), the Gender STI project launched a #WomenInScience campaign to put a spotlight on gender equality in science. We spoke to researchers and experts, both men and women, about the low number of women in science and what we need to do to encourage women and girls to pursue scientific careers.

We are thrilled to present this diverse collection of voices from across the world who are committed to gender equality, and hope that you'll find it informative and inspiring. Finally, we leave you with one message: Women make science better. That's a fact. Let's all work hard to make it gender equality in science a reality.

1. [Nina Rilla: "I Want to Encourage All People to Pursue a Career They Feel Passionate About"](#)

Rilla, a senior scientist at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, believes diversity and cooperation spur science, technology and innovation. She wants to encourage all people to pursue a career they feel passionate about, whether it's in science or outside science.

2. [Moacyr Martucci Jr.: "Science Is Better When It Has People Who Think Differently and Work Differently"](#)

University of São Paulo professor Martucci affirms that addressing the low number of women in science begins with promoting science and technology development in

elementary and secondary schools. He also has a message for women and girls: You are very important to science.

3. [Danielle Nadin: "More Needs to Be Done to Help Retain Girls and Women in Science Once They Get There"](#)

When we talk about increasing women in science, Danielle Nadin, science strategy lead at the Canadian Institutes of Health Research – Institute of Gender and Health, reminds us that we need to consider all women. This includes racialized, Indigenous, queer, trans, disabled, neurodivergent, low income and otherwise marginalized women.

4. [Isabel Kreiner: "We Need to Create an Equilibrium Between Work and Family Life"](#)

One of the challenges facing women in science is work-life balance. Isabel Kreiner, director of the Research Development Department at Tec de Monterrey, says we have to think of ways to keep women involved in research. One method would be allowing women to return to research after maternity leave or keeping them involved part-time during their leave.

5. [Wolfgang Slany: "Women and Girls Are Half of Humanity, and They Deserve Equal Opportunities"](#)

Wolfgang Slany, a professor at the Graz University of Technology and founder of the nonprofit Catrobat, explains that increasing the number of women in science requires a thousand faced approach, with lots of smaller and larger steps.

6. [Nawal Aït Ali: "The Lack of Women Researchers Is a Massive Loss for Science and Social Progress"](#)

Instead of encouraging women and girls to work on themselves to gain trust and self-confidence, Nawal Aït Ali, part of the Mission for the Place of Women, says we should put more institutional effort in fixing the system.

7. [Janina Onuki: "I Hope That Women and Girls Will Be Inspired by Women Scientists"](#)

Globally, less than 30% of researchers are women. Janina Onuki, professor and dean at the Institute of International Relations at the University of São Paulo, points out that this is due to the lack of conditions and opportunities offered to female researchers.

8. [Aarani Mathialagan: "We Need to Create a Culture Where Women Feel Welcome in Science"](#)

While overt gender discrimination in scientific fields may have been largely reduced, long-standing biases and stereotypes persist. Aarani Mathialagan, science communication officer at the Canadian Institutes of Health Research – Institute of Gender and Health, affirms that this can be seen in the gender gap in education and in the women leaving STEM fields at higher rates than men.

9. [Silvia de los Ríos Pérez: "Women and Girls Still Need More References in Science That Empower Them"](#)

Having women role models in science is key if we want to increase the number of women in science. Silvia de los Ríos Pérez, researcher and project manager in the LifeSTech research group at the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, says increasing visibility for women researchers is one way to create more empowering references for women.

10. [Vesna Krnjic: "You Can Do Anything in Science If You Believe in Yourself"](#)

Women interested in science need to believe in themselves when pursuing a scientific career. Vesna Krnjic, a researcher at the Graz University of Technology, reminds young women if they're curious and their heart beats for science, a scientific career is just for them.

11. [Anna Ginès i Fabrellas: "Women Are Leaking Through the Cracks of the Scientific Pipeline"](#)

The concept of the "leaky pipeline" is a big issue when talking about gender equality in science and academia. Anna Ginès i Fabrellas, associate professor at ESADE Law School and coordinator of the Equal4Europe project, explains that women face many barriers in their educational journeys and in the workplace, which leads some of them to leave the field.

12. [Yvonne Vermonden: "Women in Science Need to Be Offered the Same Opportunities as Men"](#)

To increase the number of women in science, we need to think about the environment that they work in and the opportunities they're offered. Yvonne Vermonden, senior consultant at Nehem, points out that women need to be as actively encouraged as men.

13. [Silvia Kochen: "Fight for Everything You Want in Science and in Life"](#)

It is well known that work-life balance is a big challenge facing women in science. Some women even might feel that they have to choose between following their scientific dreams and having a family. Silvia Kochen, a neuroscience researcher at CONICET and an extraordinary woman in science, has a message for women and girls: Fight for everything you want.

14. [Surbhi Sharma: "Let's Focus on the Women Heroes in Science"](#)

We have to remember our women heroes in science locally and on a global level. Surbhi Sharma, founder of the Euro India Research Centre (EIRC), reminds us that women in science have already created amazing things and that their future is limitless.

15. [Matteo Avogaro: "Women and Men Must Fight for Gender Equality in Science Together"](#)

In the fight for equality in science, women and men need to work together to break gender barriers. We need men scientists as allies. One of them is Matteo Avogaro, postdoctoral researcher at the Esade Institute for Labour Studies, who points out that working in an environment where men and women are equally represented is good for research because it allows you to see different perspectives.

16. [Sarina Gursch: "You Can Create Much More in Science as a Community"](#)

Having more women in science will not only create a diverse environment, they will also create a vibrant scientific community. Sarina Gursch, a researcher at the Graz University of Technology, reminds us of the strength of community in science.

17. [Yolanda Ursa: "We Need a Global Commitment to Overcome Gender Stereotypes in Science"](#)

Globally, there are cultural barriers and gender stereotypes that attribute certain roles and values to women, which is something that happens in scientific careers. Yolanda

Ursa, director of innovation management at Inmark Europa and scientific coordinator at Gender STI, says we need an international commitment to overcome these challenges.

18. [Catarina Milhazes: "Gender Equality in Science Starts With Changing the Perception Bias"](#)

A critical challenge facing women in science is the perception bias. Catarina Milhazes, an international cooperation and development consultant at the Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação, explains that tackling bias begins by addressing how we teach brilliance at a young age.

19. [Julian Anslinger: "Policy Makers and Universities Must Ensure All People Have Equal Opportunities"](#)

When discussing women in science, we have to analyze the support structures they have. Julian Anslinger, a researcher and member of the CHANGE project, says this is crucial. If key actors don't create structures and conditions under which all people have equal opportunities, young girls and women will have to create their own support structures.

20. [Cecilia Matsumura: "Social Policies Are Tools to Address Gender Inequality in Science"](#)

Throughout history, women have been pushed aside in science and have had to fight for their place. Cecilia Matsumura, a woman scientist from the University of São Paulo, points out that although women's roles have been changing, recognition of women and opportunities for them have not kept pace with this evolution.

21. [Sandhya Venkatesh: "Women and Girls Must Be Given Examples of Women Scientists and Their Impact"](#)

Sandhya Venkatesh, a project manager at the Euro India Research Centre, believes there is much more scope for women to participate in science and research and that it has to be encouraged in all countries equally. Encouraging women and girls to pursue science starts by giving visibility to brilliant women scientists and turning them into role models.

22. [Ana Carolina Gomes: "Remember the Brilliant Women Who Cleared the Path for You"](#)

While there is still a long way to go before we achieve gender equality in science, it's important to remember that change starts with every one of us. Ana Carolina Gomes, a Senior International Project Manager and Consultant at the Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação, affirms that we have the opportunity to give a voice to diverse individuals in science.

ANNEX 3 – BLOG FOR IWG 2021 I

#WomenInLeadership: Celebrating Leaders in Science, Technology and Innovation on International Women's Day 2021

[NEWS](#)

03.03.2021

In honor of [International Women's Day 2021](#), Gender STI is launching a “#WomenInLeadership” campaign, which aims to celebrate women leaders in science, technology and innovation and shed light on their journeys, challenges and goals.

The campaign was inspired by the United Nation's theme for International Women's Day 2021, “Women in leadership: Achieving an equal future in a COVID-19 world.” Through their work, there is no doubt that every single woman in the Gender STI campaign is breaking gender barriers and using science, technology and innovation (STI) to create a better world.

All of the women in the campaign were nominated by one of the partners in the Gender STI consortium. Partners nominated women leaders who work passionately with their teams to expand scientific knowledge, use STI for the benefit of society and support other scientists and innovators.

In total, Gender STI received 22 nominations of extraordinary women leaders from 11 countries: Austria, Brazil, Canada, China, India, Lebanon, Mexico, South Africa, South Korea, Spain and the U.S. We are featuring all of their stories over the next few days on our website and social media channels.

Nominees include women researchers, professors, current and former government officials, industry leaders, innovation directors and inclusive designers, among many others.

To follow the campaign and join in on the conversation, use the hashtag #WomenInLeadership as well as the official IWD hashtag, #IWD2021. You can follow our activity on our official [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [Facebook](#) pages, as well as on the [news section](#) of our website.

At Gender STI, it is an honor to recognize these amazing women leaders from across the globe. We have learned so much about leadership, gender equality, perseverance and believing in yourself from our wonderful nominees over the past few weeks. Although all their stories were different, there was one common theme in nearly all of the responses: Women's voices matter and they deserve to be heard.

When we as a society listen to women and include them in decision-making, there are no limits to what we can achieve.

ANNEX 3 – BLOG FOR IWG 2021 II

22 Lessons From Women Leaders in Science, Technology and Innovation for International Women's Day 2021

[NEWS](#)

09.03.2021

For [International Women's Day](#), the Gender STI project [launched #WomenInLeadership](#), a campaign to celebrate women leaders in science, technology and innovation (STI). Our partners nominated a variety of women leaders who were making a difference in their communities and fields, from professors and researchers to business executives and political leaders.

On the big day, we featured 22 extraordinary women leaders from 11 countries across the globe.

Each woman leader was featured in a profile. We asked them about challenges faced in their leadership journey, their goals as a leader, the advice they would give young women and girls who want to be leaders one day and what we need to do to increase the number women leaders in STI. Their answers are full of wisdom, strength, generosity and inspiration.

Being a leader requires lifelong learning. As such, we're thrilled to bring you 22 lessons we learned from our amazing women leaders in STI. For Gender STI, the biggest takeaway was clear: We need to advocate for more women leaders. Gender equality is beneficial for all of society, and more women leaders in STI will help take us to places we never thought possible.

Click on the link to read the nominee's profile in full.

1. [Hui Luo: Having a Career and a Family Is Possible](#)

“Some people think that career and family are just like the sun and the stars and that they cannot be shining at the same time; we must abandon one. However, I am committed to managing and integrating career advancement and our son’s education together. I believe it is the continuous observation and study that makes it possible... I am still exploring and determining ways to attain better balance. Often, it is not easy, but the challenge and energy is worth every little bit of effort I give to it.”

Luo is the Executive Director of the [China Centre for International Science and Technology Exchange \(CISTE\)](#) and the New Technology Development Center of the [China Association for Science and Technology \(CAST\)](#).

2. [Heisook Lee: Increasing the Number of Women Leaders in STI Begins by Changing Mindsets Early On](#)

“To increase the number of women leaders in STI, the first step should be to recruit more girls and women into STEM by building an inclusive culture, fighting gender stereotype and biases, and changing mindsets beginning in their early childhood. I would suggest building a mentoring platform that provides lifelong learning opportunities beyond fields and generations. In the platform, women leaders can play a pivotal role by sharing their experience of how they overcame obstacles, empowering other women and mentoring them as role models.”

Lee is the President of the [Center for Gendered Innovations in Science and Technology Research \(GISTeR\)](#) and a Professor Emeritus at [Ewha Womans University](#) in Seoul.

3. [Tamara Elzein: Gender Equality in Leadership Requires Bottom-Up and Top-Down Approaches](#)

“We need to adopt bottom-up and top-down approaches. We need to promote science and technology careers among girls and young women, to put in place empowerment and capacity building programs, and to build networks that shed light on women’s achievements. On the other hand, institutions and political authorities must make the effort to adopt egalitarian policies to promote women in decision-making positions.”

Elzein is currently the Director of Research at the [National Council for Scientific Research of Lebanon \(CNRS-L\)](#) and the Director of the National Doctoral Fellowships Program.

4. [Vikki Ho: Don’t Deprive the World of an Idea That Can Only Be Ignited by You](#)

“I would say that we all have something worthy to contribute and that science benefits from having a diverse group of people around the table. Your voice and your opinion are a unique combination of your upbringing, intellect and you! By doubting yourself, you are depriving the world of an idea that can only be ignited by you. Women bring something different to the table in terms of the way we interact and the way we approach issues. We should be proud of our differences and make sure they have an impact.”

Ho is an Assistant Professor and Researcher at the University of Montreal and the Hospital Research Centre. She holds the Canadian Institutes of Health Research's [Chair in Sex and Gender Science](#) in [Cancer Research](#).

5. [Cristiani Vieira Machado: Family Support Can Be Crucial to Reconcile Work, Research and Motherhood](#)

“My two daughters were born while I was a Ph.D candidate, and family support was crucial to face the challenges of conciliating work, study and maternity. I think that I overcame the main obstacles with persistent and hard work, and by believing in teamwork. I also was inspired by other women, and I had a lot of support from my family, academic supervisors, professors and colleagues (especially from other women).

But, as a middle-class woman born in a big city (Rio de Janeiro), in a very unequal country, it is important to recognize that most women face a lot more difficulties and obstacles than I did, such as black women and poor women living in regions or areas with less opportunities. And I feel responsible, as a scientist and a public official, to take action to change this unequal and unfair scenario.”

Machado is the Vice-president of Education, Information and Communication at [Fiocruz](#). She is also a public health researcher.

6. [Jutta Treviranus: Imagine a Community That Enables the Widest Spectrum of Perspectives and Enables the Full Participation of People on the Margins of Society](#)

“My goals as a leader echo my goals as an inclusive designer. My goal is to foster a very diverse and inclusive community. I want to create a community that includes the widest spectrum of perspectives and enables the full participation of people with lived experience of the margins of our society. That is how we foster dynamic resilience, and a community that can learn from mistakes, has more innovative choices, is cognizant of the weak signals of issues to come, and cares for us during inevitable crises.”

Treviranus is the director and founder of the [Inclusive Design Research Centre \(IDRC\)](#) and professor at [OCAD University](#) in Toronto, Canada.

7. [Hee-Young Paik: To Increase the Number of Women Leaders, We Need to Think of Practical Ways to Help Them at Home](#)

“First, we need to increase women in science and technology (S&T) fields. Currently, we have fair proportion of women in biological fields, but not in math, physical sciences and engineering. We need much more advances in technology fields.

Second, we need to encourage women to go into leadership positions. Since women tend to take more responsibilities at home, women in S&T are exhausted, and tend not to prefer to take any positions with responsibilities. We need practical ways to help with housework and family responsibilities so that women in S&T would not hesitate to take more responsibility.”

Paik is a board member of the [Center for Gendered Innovations in Science and Technology Research \(GISTeR\)](#) and a Professor Emeritus at [Seoul National University](#) in South Korea. Paik served as the South Korean government's Minister of Gender Equality and Family from 2009 to 2011.

8. [Stefanie Lindstaedt: Create a Vision of Yourself, and Then Make It Come True](#)

“Believe in yourself, your ideas and set challenging goals for yourself. Find like-minded people to work together and develop new ideas. Young girls and women are often told that striving for power is bad. But power implies the chance to follow your own vision. Question yourself, what kind of vision of yourself would you like to see come true? And then, go for it.”

Lindstaedt is the CEO of [Know-Center Graz](#) and Director of the [Institute for Interactive Systems and Data Science \(ISDS\)](#) at the Graz University of Technology.

9. [María Fernanda Cabrera: Don't Conform or Pretend to be Somebody You're Not](#)

“I would tell [young girls and women] not to conform or pretend to be somebody they are not. They should focus on their strengths and abilities, do what they think is right and, most importantly, remain authentic. In my opinion, this will inevitably make them excel.”

Cabrera is the Innovation Director of the [LifeSTech](#) research group and an Associate Professor at the Telecommunications School at the [Universidad Politécnica de Madrid](#).

10. [Judy van Biljon: The Quest for Women's Equality Is a Marathon, and Each One of Us Have a Lap to Run](#)

“Gendered power imbalances are centuries in the making and lie deep within our social fabric. The quest for women's equality is a marathon, not a sprint and each one of us have a lap to run in this equality relay race. The contribution lies in receiving the baton, competing hard to close the gap and then leaving the next woman competitor in a better position. We may not achieve equality in our time, but we will forever be part of the women who contributed towards equality in science, technology and innovation.”

Van Biljon is a Professor of Information Systems and holds the National Research Foundation's Chair in Information and Communication for Development hosted by the School of Computing at the [University of South Africa \(Unisa\)](#).

11. [Neeloffer Mookherjee: Leaders Are Not Created Alone](#)

“[R]emember it takes a village; work together, hear each other, and as a leader promote the voices of women who feel they don't belong. To me the most important skills as a leader are that of empathy and the ability to listen.

We all need mentors, at all stages, albeit mentors change as we evolve in our careers. To that end, I would encourage women to seek out mentors, as well as pay it forward by

becoming a mentor to women in your professional field. You will always have younger women and girls coming up behind you who can benefit from your experience, no matter the level you are currently at.”

Mookherjee is a Professor at the [University of Manitoba](#) in Canada and the Canadian Institutes of Health Research's (CIHR) [Sex and Gender Science Chair](#) in [Respiratory Health](#).

12. [Patricia Ellen: Girls Can Be Leaders in Anything They Want to Be](#)

“Although we still have a long way to go, we must acknowledge that a great effort has been put into raising awareness about how girls can be anything they want to be. To that, I’d add that “girls can be leaders in anything they want to be.” It is important to include the word “leaders” in that, so that young girls understand that that can not only become scientists but also lead science and technology decision-making. Inspiring others, coordinating teams, solving complex problems and other responsibilities like that are part of being a leader and we are not used to teaching young girls to aspire such things, but we can do that.”

Ellen is the Secretary of Economic Development, Science and Technology for the State of São Paulo.

13. [Kiran Mazumdar Shaw: The Funnel Effect Is What Needs to Be Stopped](#)

“We clearly see that entry level is not the problem. The funnel effect is what needs to be stopped. Focus on policies that incentivize both men and women to support gender balance initiatives.”

Mazumdar Shaw is the Executive Chairperson of [Biocon](#), India’s largest biopharmaceutical company. She is a first-generation entrepreneur and global business leader with over four decades of experience in biotechnology.

14. [Glaudina Loots: By Being a Woman Leader, You Make It Easier for the Next Group of Young Women to Follow in Your Steps](#)

“[It] is important to focus on your dreams and to strive for what you feel is important. Achievements by women in science leadership positions are made all the more valuable as aside from overcoming difficult paths to get there, you made it easier for the next group of young women to follow and further progress the field.”

Loots is the Director for Health Innovation at the [Department of Science and Innovation](#) in South Africa.

15. [Salma Jalife: Women Should Relate to Other Women Leaders in the Fields They Want to Pursue](#)

“While there are increasingly more girls entering STEM careers, there are still biases, social norms and family expectations, factors they must face in order to be able to

succeed as leaders. However, it is very important that they do not leave their dreams to become what they believe they can be in the future. I suggest they relate to women leaders in the field they want to pursue, seek mentoring from women groups in their social networks, read success stories about women overcoming discrimination and barriers to become leaders, and above all, focus on accumulating knowledge and expertise in their academic development. Teachers, men and women, who promote growth for young girls and women are great allies.”

Jalife is the CEO and founder of Centro México Digital (CMD). Previously, Jalife was the Subsecretary of Communications in the Department of Communications and Transport of the Mexican government.

16. [Padma Kaul: "Young Women Shouldn't Be Disheartened If They Are Not Successful at First"](#)

“I would say to young girls what I say to my two teenage daughters: do well in math, pursue science subjects (physics, chemistry, biology, computer science) in high school and beyond.

To young women starting their professional careers, I would tell them to find good mentors and role models; to be persistent in their efforts and not be disheartened if they are not successful at first.”

Kaul is a professor at the [University of Alberta](#), an adjunct professor at Duke University and the co-director of the [Canadian VIGOUR Centre](#). Kaul is the [CIHR Sex and Gender Chair in Diabetes](#) and the Heart & Stroke Chair in Cardiovascular Research.

17. [María Teresa Arredondo: Let's Not Let Motherhood, Marriage, Life as a Couple or Social Paradigms Keep Us From Living Our Dreams](#)

“Let's not let some issues that have traditionally been a problem—such as motherhood, marriage, life as a couple, or the different social paradigms that are still behind regarding the role of women—keep us from our happiness. Because I have a family, I have children and many other women do too; and I believe that we all have the right to feel fulfilled and to achieve the goals that we propose in life, regardless of gender, social class or ethnicity. We all have the right to live our dreams. And I think that when you know what you want, you can get it.”

She is the director and founder of the LifeSTech Research Group and a biomedical engineering professor at the [Universidad Politécnica de Madrid](#).

18. [Liedi Bernucci: Leaders Don't Have to Be 100% Prepared to Lead](#)

“We need to have more women in all sectors. I think we have to say that they don't need to be 100% prepared to lead, as they will learn by doing their work. Nobody knows everything before they are working and experiencing leadership.”

Bernucci is the Dean of the [Polytechnic School of the Universidade de São Paulo](#) and a Full Professor for Infrastructure and Transportation Engineering.

19. [Aleksandra Krstikj: We Need Culture-Sensitive Supportive Infrastructure to Give Women the Choice of Pursuing a Career in STI and Becoming a Leader](#)

“It is not only about opening more job positions for women leaders in STI. Women in different parts of the world have different cultural and social norms which restrict their development. Thus, I think policies about gender balance in STI have to be accompanied by more culture-sensitive supportive infrastructure that will create the conditions for a woman to have the choice of pursuing a career in STI and becoming a leader.

Moreover, even though the number of women in STI might have increased, little has been done to ensure equal wages and consideration of maternity responsibilities for women in leading positions.”

Krstikj is a full-time research professor at [Tec de Monterrey](#)'s School of Architecture, Art, and Design. She is also the leader of the national research group (GIEE) "Sustainable Territorial Development" of the School of Architecture, Art and Design at Tec.

20. [Rocío Ortiz López: Institutions Should Educate, Prepare and Train Women for Positions](#)

“If there are jobs where women constitute a minority and there are no female candidates to fill vacant positions, companies and institutions should undertake the task of educating, preparing, and training women to fill these positions. There should be policies in place so that executive or leadership positions are rotated between men and women.

This way, women would genuinely be encouraged to participate equitably in any position in STI and, in consequence, it would promote an increase of women leaders in these fields.”

Ortiz is professor at [Tec de Monterrey](#) and leader of a cancer research group.

21. [May D. Wang: To Overcome Bias, Be Nice, Assertive and Extremely Technically Competent](#)

“I have faced many challenges early on in my career. I received my MSCS and Ph.D. degree in Electrical and Computer Engineering from Georgia Institute of Technology more than 20 years ago. At that time, the percentage of women Ph.Ds. was low. Initially, my voice was ignored often.

Then when I was recruited back to Georgia Institute of Technology with my husband as a two-body hire into Emory University, I was still called his wife more often than I was called Professor Wang. I overcame these challenges by doing three things I learned: be nice, be assertive, and be extremely technically competent by working doubly hard.”

Wang is a professor at the [Georgia Institute of Technology and Emory University](#) and director of the Biomedical Big Data Initiative.

22. [Rachel Chikwamba: Don't Let Anybody Limit You](#)

“The sky is the limit, and that gender has nothing to do with their possibilities. In fact, I would point [young girls and women] to role models in the space and encourage them to not be self-limiting. If they are not self-limiting in their perspective and ambition, then certainly no one has the right to limit them. They should not allow it; they should make their dreams real and claim their spots in the fields of their dreams!”

Chikwamba is the Group Executive: Chemicals, Agriculture, Food and Health at [CSIR](#).

ANNEX 4 – CAMPAIGN MENTIONS BY PARTNERS AND THIRD PARTIES

Source: Agência FAPESP

Reference Link: [Here](#)

Diretora da Poli-USP é reconhecida líder de destaque pelo Gender STI

16 de março de 2021

Agência FAPESP * – [Liedi Bernucci](#), diretora da Escola Politécnica da Universidade de São Paulo (Poli-USP) e membro do Conselho Superior da FAPESP, está entre as 22 mulheres, de 11 países, indicadas como líderes excepcionais em ciência, tecnologia e inovação, pelo projeto internacional de pesquisa [Gender STI](#).

Liedi Bernucci está entre as 22 mulheres de 11 países consideradas líderes excepcionais em ciência, tecnologia e inovação (foto: Associação dos Engenheiros Politécnicos/divulgação)

Source: University of São Paulo

Reference Link: [Here](#)

ESCOLA POLITÉCNICA
FORMANDO ENGENHEIROS E LÍDERES

USP

[Institucional](#) [Ensino](#) [Pesquisa](#) [Cultura e Extensão](#) [Bibliotecas](#) [Profissionais e Empresas](#) [Internacional](#)

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HOME / NOTÍCIAS / DESTAQUE / DIRETORA DA POLI-USP É RECONHECIDA COMO LÍDER DE DESTAQUE EM CAMPANHA INTERNACIONAL

Diretora da Poli-USP é reconhecida como líder de destaque em campanha internacional

Liedi Bernucci é uma das 22 indicadas pelo projeto Gender STI, um grupo de pesquisa internacional que analisa a participação das mulheres em ciência, tecnologia e inovação

Source: University of South Africa

Reference Link: [Here](#)

College of Science, Engineering & Technology

"The quest for women's equality is a marathon and each one of us have a lap to run"

GenderSTI

Judy van Bijlon
SARChI Chair in Information and Communication for Development
University of South Africa

#WOMENINLEADERSHIP

Judy van Biljon was nominated for Gender STI's [#WomenInLeadership Campaign](#), which celebrates women leaders in science, technology and innovation, by the [Council for Scientific and Industrial Research](#) in South Africa.

She is a Professor of Information Systems and holds the National Research Foundation's Chair in Information and Communication for Development hosted by the School of Computing at the [University of South Africa \(Unisa\)](#). Van Biljon has contributed to the body of academic knowledge by publishing on Human-Computer Interaction evaluation and interaction design for marginalised groups, technology adoption, and sustainability in digital learning for resource-constrained environments.

Van Biljon spoke to Gender STI about her experience as a woman leader in honour of [International Women's Day 2021](#).

Source: Tecnológico de Monterrey

Reference Link: [Here](#)

'Toda mujer líder de hoy es una icebreaker'

Aleksandra Krstikj, investigadora del Tec de Monterrey, fue nominada para la iniciativa internacional Gender STI, y en entrevista narra su experiencia como mujer líder en honor al Día Internacional de la Mujer.

7 marzo, 2021

Aleksandra Krstikj was nominated for Gender STI's [#WomenInLeadership Campaign](#), which celebrates women leaders in science, technology and innovation, by [Tecnológico de Monterrey](#) in Mexico.

She is a full-time research professor at Tec de Monterrey's School of Architecture, Art, and Design. Her research focuses on problems related to urban conservation of historic centers and sustainable land use in the metropolitan periphery. Krstikj is a member of the National System of Researchers of Mexico and the Architectural Institute of Japan. She is also the leader of the national research group (GIEE) «Sustainable Territorial Development» of the School of Architecture, Art and Design at Tec. Dr. Krstikj is the coordinator of the Urbanism cluster in the Post Covid-19 Think Tank in the Vice-rector's Office for Research at Tec, which is focused on recovery and urban development post covid-19.

Source: Tecnológico de Monterrey

Reference Link: [Here](#)

‘Las mujeres deben seguir sus instintos y ser persistentes y apasionadas’

Rocío Ortiz, investigadora del Tec de Monterrey, fue nominada para la iniciativa internacional Gender STI, y en entrevista narra su experiencia como mujer líder en honor al Día Internacional de la Mujer.

7 marzo, 2021

Rocío Ortiz López was nominated for [Gender STI's #WomenInLeadership Campaign](#), which celebrates women leaders in science, technology and innovation, by [Tecnológico de Monterrey](#) in Mexico.

She is professor at Tec de Monterrey and leader of a cancer research group. Ortiz specialized in molecular biology of disease and genomic medicine but slowly made her way into the area of cancer. She likes finding out and implementing methodological tools that allow for the research of this disease. The ultimate goal of her research is to identify molecular and metabolic targets that might work as clinical tools to enhance early cancer detection, improve therapies and reduce mortality.

Source: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid**Reference Link:** [Here](#)

“Estoy orgullosa de trabajar en un grupo de investigación mayoritariamente liderado por mujeres”

Con motivo del Día Internacional de la Mujer, María Fernanda Cabrera, directora de innovación del grupo LifeStech de la ETSI Telecomunicación explica los retos a los que se ha enfrentado y sobre cómo ha desarrollado su carrera hasta convertirse en una reconocida investigadora.

08.03.2021

María Fernanda Cabrera fue nominada para la campaña #WomenInLeadership de Gender STI, que trata de visibilizar y dar un reconocimiento a las mujeres líderes en ciencia, tecnología e innovación, por sus trabajos en el Grupo de Investigación LifeSTech de la Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM).

Source: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid**Reference Link:** [Here](#)

"A las niñas y las mujeres les diría que no estén disponibles para el desánimo"

La iniciativa europea para promover la igualdad de género en la ciencia, la tecnología y la innovación entrevista a nuestra catedrática María Teresa Arredondo con motivo del Día Internacional de la Mujer.

08.03.2021

María Teresa Arredondo estuvo nominada para la campaña mujeres líderes de Gender STI que trata de poner en relieve el liderazgo y la innovación desarrollados por mujeres en ciencia tecnología e innovación. La candidatura fue un reconocimiento a su trabajo en el grupo LifeStech de la ETSI de Telecomunicación de la UPM.

Directora y fundadora de dicho grupo de investigación y catedrática de ingeniería biomédica en la UPM, Arredondo fue también la primera mujer en convertirse en catedrática de Telecomunicaciones y Bioingeniería en España, algo que logró en 2001. Fue, además, la única mujer en lograrlo durante 10 años. Es una de las creadoras de la Sociedad Argentina de Ingeniería Biomédica y la primera secretaria de dicha institución. Arredondo es también la responsable de las relaciones con Latinoamérica en la UPM y la directora de la cátedra Vodafone para la Salud y la Inclusión.

Source: REUNA**Reference Link:** [Here](#)

#WomenInLeadership: Celebrando a las líderes en CTI en el Día Internacional de la Mujer 2021

MARZO 4, 2021

En honor al Día Internacional de la Mujer 2021, el proyecto Gender STI está lanzando la campaña “#WomenInLeadership”, que tiene como objetivo celebrar a las mujeres líderes en Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación (CTI) y arrojar luz sobre sus viajes, desafíos y objetivos.

La campaña se inspiró en el tema de las Naciones Unidas para el Día Internacional de la Mujer 2021, “Mujeres en el liderazgo: Lograr un futuro equitativo en un mundo COVID-19”. A través de su trabajo, no hay duda de que todas las mujeres de la campaña de género en CTI están rompiendo las barreras de género y utilizando la ciencia, la tecnología y la innovación para crear un mundo mejor.

Todas las Noticias
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Categorías

- CASOS DE USO (2)
- EVENTOS (753)
- CONFERENCIAS (6)
- CONGRESOS (5)
- SEMINARIOS (8)

Source: IDRC Newsletter**Reference Link:** [Here](#)

IDRC News

Gender STI

Gender Equality in Science, Technology and Innovation

The IDRC is excited to be a partner in the Gender STI project. Gender STI is an international research project that aims to analyze the participation of women in **science, technology and innovation (STI) dialogues between Europe and third countries**. The project will focus on **four key areas**:

1. Gender equality in scientific careers
2. Gender balance in decision-making
3. Integrating gender dimension in **Research and Innovation (R&I)** content
4. Co-designing solutions to common challenges found in these areas through a design-thinking process

The **Gender STI** consortium is made up of partners from **sixteen countries in four continents**. The project is honouring **International Women's Day 2021** with the **#WomenInLeadership** campaign, which celebrates women leaders in science, technology and innovation and sheds light on their journeys, challenges and goals.

Source: Inmark**Reference Link:** [Here](#)

Inmark Europa comparte el reconocimiento a 22 mujeres líderes de 11 países en el Día Internacional de la Mujer a través del proyecto Gender STI

Por Inmark | 8 marzo 2021 | Blog Público | Comentarios desactivados

ANNEX 5 – NEWSLETTER CAMPAIGNS FOR DISSEMINATION

Invitation to the Gender STI Community of Practice and Dissemination of Survey Report

GENDER STI CO-DESIGN LABS:
Tackling Gender Equality in STI Worldwide
ONLINE

SEP 13, 14, 15 and 16
OCT 5 and 7

Thank you for participating in the Co-Design Labs!

Hi <<First Name>>,

We wanted to take a moment to extend our gratitude for taking the time and effort to participate in Gender STI's first Co-Design Labs. Our team was thrilled to have perspectives on gender equality in STI from all over the world! Your input has helped us create prototypes that will contribute to advancing gender equality, which we look forward to sharing with you soon.

You are now part of the **Gender STI Community of Practice**, and we'll be in touch to share project research, activities and events with you. As such, we want you all to be the first to receive our first project results, which consist of a [Survey Report on Gender Equality in International Cooperation](#).

We hope the knowledge gained from the Co-Design Labs allows and inspires you to push for gender equality in your organizations and countries. No initiative is too small. After all, change begins with a single step.

Kind regards,

Yolanda Ursa

SURVEY ON
Gender Equality in
STI Bilateral and
Multilateral Agreements

GenderSTI+ 2021

Our report presents the results of an international survey on gender equality in international cooperation. Gender STI carried out the survey earlier this year.

[View Survey Report](#)

December 2021 Newsletter

Gender STI

December 2021 Newsletter

Dear Gender STI Community,

It's been a busy couple of months for the project! Gender STI is now a little more than one year old, and we couldn't have gotten here without your support. This in mind, we want you all to be some of the first people to receive our big project results.

Survey on Gender Equality in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements

We're pleased to share our ["Report on Gender Equality Implementation in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements,"](#) which presents the results of our survey on the state of gender equality in STI international cooperation agreements.

Promoting Gender STI

Besides releasing the results of our survey, the Gender STI project has also been hard at work promoting the project in Europe, Asia, Africa, and North and South America.

Most recently, the project participated in Argentina's Second ["Women and the Brain Conference,"](#) which was co-organized by the Argentine Network on Gender, Science, and Technology (RAGCyT), a Gender STI partner.

Learn more [here](#).

CEREBRO Y MUJER II
MITOS, REALIDADES, DISTINTAS PERSPECTIVAS

VIERNES 26 DE NOVIEMBRE 18 HS

<p>DIANA SUÁREZ Economista, CIEPIBA, Economía del Conocimiento-IDE/UNGS, CECTI</p> <p>Equidad de género y producción de conocimiento: Prácticas y desafíos en el mundo post-covid19</p>	<p>FLORENCIA FIORENTÍN Economista, Economía del Conocimiento, Univ. Nac. Gral. Sarmiento</p> <p>Dibujando mitos sobre la "objetividad" del conocimiento: la importancia de avanzar hacia una agenda de ciencia y tecnología feminista</p>	<p>YOLANDA URSA Directora de Sesión de la Innovación, Inmark Europe, Coord. científica del proyecto GENDER STI</p> <p>Igualdad de Género en los Acuerdos de Cooperación Interdisciplinaria en Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación</p>
<p>CLAUDIA BRIONES Antropóloga Inv. del CONICET y Prof. de la Univ. Nac. Rio Negro en el IDyPCA</p> <p>Lo personal es político y lo académico también: ¿cuándo y cómo el género deviene o no agenda de investigación?</p>	<p>DORA BARRANCOS Bióloga, CONICET, Investigadora del Consejo Asesor Min. de las Mujeres, Ciencia y Diversidad de la Nación Argentina, Asesora Presidencial</p> <p>Palabras de cierre: De la "realización masculinista" a la rigencia de la cultura</p>	

LA ACTIVIDAD SERÁ PRESENCIAL EN TECNÓPOLIS Y VIRTUAL

INSCRIPCIÓN PREVIA Y MÁS INFORMACIÓN EN: enys.conicet.gov.ar/cerebro-y-mujer-2021

Supporting and Applauding the Ljubljana Declaration

The Gender STI project applauds the recent [Ljubljana Declaration](#) on gender equality in research and innovation, which acknowledges the importance of gender equality to the integrity and societal responsibility of research and urges signatories to be proactive in the creation of an inclusive scientific community.

We believe the declaration will set an important precedent in the drafting of new international cooperation agreements and renewal of existing agreements, establishing gender equality provisions in science, technology, and innovation as necessary for the advancement and prosperity of society.

Learn more [here](#).

Going Forward

Gender STI still has a long way to go on its journey. We have exciting activities planned for 2022, so make sure you stay tuned. Don't forget to follow us on social media and check out our website!

Kind regards,
Yolanda Ursa
Gender STI Scientific Coordinator

2021 Year in Review

Gender STI

YEAR 2021 IN
REVIEW

Gender STI in 2021: A Year in Review

Dear Gender STI subscriber,

It's been a long year! Although 2021 hasn't been without its challenges, there has also been progress. For our project, it was the year that marked the beginning of our research journey and one that produced our first results.

We couldn't have gotten this far without your enthusiasm and support, and we wanted to take the last day of the year to celebrate what the Gender STI project has accomplished so far. This includes:

- **Launch of #WomenInLeadership campaign:** Early in the year, we launched a #WomenInLeadership campaign to celebrate women leaders in STI for International Women's Day. We featured 22 extraordinary women leaders from across the globe who are making a difference in their communities and fields. You can check out the [lessons they taught us here](#).

- **Completion of the “Survey on Gender Equality Implementation in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements”:** In 2021, we carried out our first major research activity when we launched our survey on gender equality in international cooperation agreements between Europe and third countries. The survey allowed us to gain important insights on what issues are important in the fight for gender equality and how priorities may differ according to region. You can read our full report [here](#).
- **Launch of the project’s first Co-Design Labs:** We were thrilled to welcome experts, researchers, company representatives, funding agencies, consulting companies, and universities to our first [Co-Design Labs](#). The event analyzed the biggest issues facing women in three key focus areas: scientific careers, decision-making, and the gender perspective in research and innovation content.
- **Creation of the Gender STI Community of Practice:** All participants from the Co-Design Labs were invited to join the project’s [Community of Practice](#), which aims to promote gender equality in STI in participants’ organizations and countries.
- **Publication of the project’s first Co-Design Lab prototypes:** Furthermore, we have [published the prototypes](#) developed by participants of the Co-Design Labs and submitted them to the European Commission for review.

You can read more about the other exciting things we’ve done, such as our campaigns on women in science and our workshop at IEEE BHI – BSN, on our blog [here](#).

Here’s to 2021. Stay tuned, we have no doubt we’ll do even more meaningful work in the year to come.

Happy new year!

Kind regards,

Jody Serrano
Gender STI Communication Manager

**GENDER STI
CO-DESIGN
LABS:**
Tackling Gender
Equality in STI
Worldwide

ONLINE

SEP 13, 14, 15 and 16
OCT 5 and 7

Gender STI

Just published: Our report on the project’s first Co-Design Labs, which includes a look at the prototypes for gender equality developed by participants.

[View Co-Design Lab Report](#)